

WHAT TO TEACH AND HOW TO TEACH IN TEACHING CHILDREN IN UZBEKISTAN CONTEXT

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ANNOTATION

In general, elementary learners will appreciate a relatively fast-paced schedule, with a lively progression from one activity to the next. However, when budgeting time, it's important to weigh which activities receive the lion's share of your school day. For example, before a reading activity, it can be useful to provide a "lead-in" lesson, introducing themes from the reading; after the reading, follow-up questions can reinforce students' reading comprehension. Be sure to factor these activities into your total time allocated for reading; while they can be useful activities, they should not infringe on the class time reserved for reading, itself.

Key words: *purposeful, effective, active engagement, lead-in, language structure, cooperative.*

Language is also an important way for us to make sense out of our past experience, to learn from it, and to make it comprehensible. In the beginning, children's language growth comes from their direct experience. It is personal and related to the present. As their language understanding grows, children can relate to ever more expanding situations. This early language experience is necessary to be able to use language symbols apart from actual situations. Children use language metaphorically, providing evidence that for children language is creative as well as imitative. For children, language is a powerful tool for understanding the world around them. By questioning, children become active in their attempt to comprehend and learn (Lindfors, 1991; Winner, McCarthy, Kleinman, & Gardner, 1979).

Children are constantly modifying their speech depending on their audience. An example of this behavior is when children modify their speech when talking to younger children. As children develop their ability to use language, they become more and more understanding of social situations and learn how to control their own actions and thoughts. By listening to children's self-corrections, questions, and language play, we realize the extent of their knowledge of language structure. Those things that children can articulate give us an understanding of what they can comprehend. Their active, creative invention of language is amazing and unique to each child. Language development is a gradual process and reflects a child's cognitive capacities. Language is purposeful. As children play and work, they do so through language (Garcia, 1994; Lindfors, 1991; McLaughlin, 1984; Shatz & Gelman, 1973).

Children expand their development of language by relating what they already know to what they encounter. "It is only with one foot placed squarely, securely within the known, the familiar, that the child can place the other foot in the beyond" (Lindfors, 1991, p. 282). Play is a way for children to extend their language abilities; it is where new vocabulary can be introduced as well as new ways to use it. It also allows children opportunities to express their point of view, solve disagreements, and persuade peers to work together. Language play has a focus on the very language elements that children will need to consider later when they learn about language. Language is a major means of influencing thinking and behavior—that of another person or one's own. For language to expand, children need to be given many opportunities to interact. Children learn from speaking. Children need to feel socially competent and accepted to become competent language users. Language is the way children are socialized by adults and the way children learn to guide their inner voice. The central role of language is the way we communicate with other people and with ourselves (Berk & Winsler, 1995; California Department of Education, 1988; Lindfors, 1991; Tabors, 1997).

In the average child, at whatever developmental stage we observe, language is alive and well. Children's language development is a creative process that only needs a rich environment to thrive (Lindfors, 1991).

Effective Teaching Methods in Elementary Public Schools. Elementary school students benefit most from instruction that is direct, moderate to fast paced and involves them in the learning process. Teachers of elementary age children need to utilize techniques that promote active learning through hands on projects and manipulatives that demonstrate concepts. Teachers also can review, reinforce and practice reading and math skills with children in small groups to increase overall achievement.

Active Engagement

Elementary students will learn more if they can have fun while working. Teachers should give their kids many opportunities to interact with each other about what they are learning. Partner reading, think pair share and writing workshops are cooperative activities that give students a chance to practice concepts and allows the teacher to assess their understanding.

Teachers also can help their students by allowing them to engage in hands on learning. For example, when introducing the concept of multiplication, the teacher can assign partnerships and give each team a bag of seeds or beans and have them pull out the targeted number and place in a row. If multiplying by two, the teacher can have the kids add two seeds to the row. This helps students with math skills and shows them that adding and multiplying are directly related.

Small Group Instruction

Differentiated instruction is an effective technique that benefits elementary students because it recognizes that children have different ways of learning. The best way to differentiate is through small groups that are based on ability as well as learning

styles. Depending upon class size, there may be four or five groups with three to five children in each one. Grouping should be flexible as students master new skills.

Methods

We want to help your child to communicate better in English. At the British Council, many different teaching methods are used to boost students' confidence and build up positive attitudes towards language learning.

- Stories, games and other child-friendly activities are used to give students opportunities to practice listening, speaking, reading and writing English.
- We use songs, rhymes and chants to improve students' pronunciation.
- Our courses are focused more on fluency than on accuracy as we want our students to build their confidence when using English. We also incorporate a range of receptive activities in class which give students the opportunity to hear English through listening and see it through reading before they are asked to use it.
- Parents are informed of their child's progress through reports and parents' consultations. We also provide orientations and workshops as well as online resources to help parents support their children's learning at home.
- As well as ensuring we provide children with a fun and enjoyable learning experience, we also aim to help develop students' interpersonal skills such as team working and sharing.

USED BOOKS

Webster's Third Edition International Dictionary of English Language, unabridged.
– Merriam Webster, Incorporated, 1993.

Suntsova, E.N., Burmakova, E.A. The Use of case Study Method in Foreign Language Teaching // Прикладная филология: идеи, концепции, проекты: Сб. ст. VI Межд. научно-практич. конф., Часть 1. – Томск: Издательство ТПУ, 2008. – С. 87-94.

American Association of Teachers of French. Borrowed from: <http://glp.elenes.com/> on August 20, 2009.

12 Beliefs About Teaching Writing. Borrowed from: <http://www.vitia.org/wordpress/2009/06/04/12-beliefs-about-teaching-writing/> on August 20, 2009.

Standards for Foreign Language Learning in the 21st Century, 1999. Borrowed from: <http://globalteachinglearning.com/standards/5cs.shtml> on August 20, 2009.

Rebecca Benoit, Bridget Haugh. Team Teaching Tips for Foreign Language Teachers. Borrowed from: <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Benoit-TeamTeaching.html> on August 20, 2009.

Collaborative Team Teaching: A Professional Marriage. Borrowed from: <http://www.theycallmeteacher.com/2008/08/collaborative-team-teaching.html> on August 20, 2009.

Horwich, Jeff. Cracks widen in team teaching of English. Asahi Evening News 24 October 1999: Life Section.